

REINFORCEMENT EFFECT OF MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBE IN SONICATED MONOCOMPONENT EPOXY MATRIX

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SUMMARY

This work analyses the effect of multi-walled carbon nanotube content on bending modulus of an aeronautical epoxy matrix. High energy sonication was chosen among the other techniques to disperse the nanotube loading. Final results indicate that reinforcement efficiency is maximised below the statistical percolation threshold, whereas it dramatically decreases above this limit.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Epoxy matrix, Mechanical properties, Nanocomposites, Dispersion

INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, material scientists and engineers have focused a huge research activity on nanotube-based nano-composites due to the extraordinary mechanical and thermal properties shown by this particular kind of nano additives of the family of fullerene. This form of carbonaceous nanostructure represents an ideal candidate as advanced filler material not only in a neat hosting system but also as advanced matrix in traditional fiber reinforced composites. Carbon nano-composite can be defined as composite materials made up of carbon nanomaterials (nanofiber or nanotube) as reinforcing filler and other organic or inorganic phases as matrix. The combination of this nano-loaded system and other more traditional reinforcement leads to the potential development of a new generation of hybrid composite materials with exceptional behaviour for both applications and fundamental science mechanisms.

Several studies have sought to verify the reinforcement effect of CNT on the mechanical properties of polymer matrices [1-4]. Generally, these studies found that the modules of the CNT/polymer composites improved by adding only few percentages of nano-particles. Although many scientific works have been carried out or still are on progress, conflicting results about improvement in strength or fracture toughness [5-6] appear, whereas a common tendency is recorded for the enhancement effect on Young's modulus. Coleman et al. [7] have produced a systematic review comparing different studies regarding Young's modulus enhancement by adding carbon nanotubes. The authors have introduced a magnitude parameter to quantify the reinforcement effect, dE_c/dV_f , defined as the composite modulus change per volume unit fraction of CNT. According to this review paper, the highest efficiency value achieved on

nanocomposite modulus by adding CNT, is due to Xu et al. [8]. This later author reports a significant increase for the modulus, from 4.2 GPa to 5.0 GPa, measured by shaft loaded blister method at only 0.1%wt of MWCNT, with an efficiency parameter of approximately 1200 GPa.

Carbon nanotube reinforcement effect in polymeric matrix depends not only by their content within the hosting system but also by the state of dispersion within the final nano-composite. The primary problem in fabrication of a nano-composite is to ensure homogeneous dispersion of carbon nanotubes in the polymer matrix. In a CNT/polymer composite, aggregation or networking of CNT may become a defect and cause a deterioration of the mechanical properties for the final nanocomposite material. Dispersion process of carbon nanotubes represents a very complex phenomenon due to their natural tendency to bundle together due to van der Waals interactions. A non uniform dispersion can lead to many defect sites and reach resin area limiting not only the efficiency of CNT as reinforcement filler [9-12] but also electrical properties [13-15]. Efficient dispersion and possibly, the alignment of CNTs within a matrix is still a challenge and it could play the main role driving the diffusion of CNT or MWCNT as nano-reinforcement on industrial scale [16-17]. Among the different techniques, reported in the literature [18-20], high energy sonication represents a valuable and effective method to produce thermosetting based nano-composite.

Filler content, polymer type, adhesion between the resin and the filler and particle characteristics (size, size distribution, shape aspect ratio) are the most prominent factors that influence the properties of nanocomposites [21-23]. Filler content and particle size are very often considered a single factor due to their interdependence [24-25] and inter-particle distance is regarded as a controlling factor, rather than particle size or volume fraction. It has to be noted that this latter factor could also defines regions in which distinctly different mechanism behaviours are observed [26-27]. Eventually, geometrical arrangement of the filler within the hosting material is also very important, especially when the content percentage is near a critical point defining a different behaviour [28]. Percolation theory [29] can be suitably considered to describe these boundaries as percolation phenomenon is reported and well-known in many filler-matrix systems. In the case of nano-filler loading, percolation has been reported in many works for electrical property considering different polymer systems. The first evidence of percolation threshold for the electrical behaviour of CNT/polymer systems is due to Coleman et al, back in 1998 [30]. Since then, a world-wide research activity has been conducted and many important understandings and experimental observations have been published [31]. Assuming a statistical distribution of filler particles with a high aspect ratio, L/D , the excluded volume concept gives a value for the critical percolation threshold equal to $\phi_c = 1/2 * (L/D)$ [32] where L and D are respectively the carbon nanotube averaged length and diameter.

In this work, the bending modulus as function of the nanotube content has been investigated in a sonicated mono-component epoxy matrix widely used in aerospace composite structures, for which mechanical behaviour states as an issue on the final application [18]. Optical microscopy has been used to evaluate the nanotube dispersion within the resin down to the micron scale. At nanotube contents below the statistical percolation threshold for the selected kind of nanotubes, the reinforcement effect is very high. Reinforcement effect strongly decreases as the micron scale agglomerates have been optically detected within the nano-composite. Statistical percolation threshold

seems to be the nanotube concentration value which separates opposite rate behaviour of reinforcement efficiency of the nano filler.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The matrix used in this research is a commercially available thermosetting resin, denominated RTM6. It is a mono-component premixed epoxy-amine system already degassed, specifically developed to fulfil the requirements of the aeronautical and space industries for advanced liquid injection moulding processes. This system was provided by Hexcel Composites (Duxford, UK).

MWNTs were provided by Nanocyl S.A. (Belgium) and they were grown by catalytic chemical vapor-deposition (CCVD) with a purity of 90% carbon to produce the 7000 grade. The mean length of the pristine MWNTs was 10 μm , and the mean diameter was 10 nm. According to these physical characteristics, the critical percolation threshold for this kind of nanotubes is ~ 0.05 vol% or 0.1 wt%. These MWNTs were used directly without any purification.

Dispersion parameters and mechanical characterization

The composites investigated in this study were prepared using sonication process for a constant time (1 hour) at temperatures of 120°C with a nominal power of 18W. All the obtained samples were degassed in vacuum oven at 90°C for 30 min, and then cured considering an identical temperature cycle (1 h at 160°C followed by 2 h at 180°C) according to the previous kinetics results. Nanocomposite samples were prepared with a MWNTs content of 0.05 wt%, 0.1 wt%, 0.2 wt%, 0.3 wt%, 0.5 wt% fraction by weight. Dynamical mechanical analysis was carried out by using a DMA Q800 TA Instruments with a three point bending strain sweep mode. Optical microscopy analysis was carried out by using an Olimpus system type BX51 in transmitted light configuration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optical Microscopy

Figure 1 shows the optical microscopy of the series of mono component samples at different nanotubes concentration (0.05; 0.1; 0.2; 0.3; 0.5 wt%). At low nanotube content (0.05 and 0.1 wt%- Fig. 1a/b) samples appear homogeneous under optical microscope analysis, showing no micro-texture, so at least down to micron scale the sonication provides a complete dispersion of nanotube agglomerates and bundles within the hosting system.

Figure 1 - Optical microscopy of MWNTs/RTM6 samples with CNT 0.05 wt% (a); 0.1 wt% (b); 0.2 wt% (c); 0.3 wt% (d); 0.5 wt% (e).

At higher concentrations (0.3, 0.5 wt%- Fig.1d/e), optical microscopy reveals not only a sub-micrometric texture but also the formation of micro-sized nanotube agglomerates. At intermediate nanotube content (0.2 % w/w - Fig.1c) only a submicron scale texture is observed. As conclusion, a nanotube network is growing due the increasing nanotube concentration within the matrix by changing the nano loading content from 0.05 to 0.5 wt%.

According to Vigolo et al. [33], from statistical point of view, a specific concentration, namely the *statistical percolation threshold*, can be identified. This critical content coincides with the onset of a macroscopic network formation of individual nanotubes. In our case, as the nominal length and diameter of the considered nanotubes are respectively 10 μ m and 10 nm, the statistical percolation threshold would be 0.05 vol% or 0.1wt%. In the real case, this percolative theoretical limit is reduced by the likely presence of a sticky interparticles potential.

Mechanical data obtained on manufactured nanocomposite samples show a strong consistency with optical observations. In fact, the growing network is macroscopically (on the micron scale) detected only above a certain concentration level. Surely,

statistical considerations imply that above the experimental percolation limit the clustering of nanotubes cannot be missed.

Figure 2: Young's modulus of MWNT/epoxy composites vs %wt of MWNTs

Mechanical Characterization

Figure 2 shows the bending modulus as a function of the nanotube content. Up to 0.10 wt% the reinforcement effect increases reaching in the case of 0.05 wt% a value of 1780 GPa. A drop of modulus arises at 0.20 wt% and, further, the reinforcement efficiency drops as the filler concentration increases. From mechanical point of view, up to 0.1 wt% nanotubes are dispersed within the epoxy matrix at submicron level, without any evidence of clustering as reported in fig. 1 a/b and the nanotube particles act as reinforcement with a very high aspect ratio $L/D \sim 10^3$, bringing the reinforcement efficiency factor to the highest value of 1780 GPa. When micro-texture (i.e. agglomeration characterised by optical size) appears, see fig. 1c, at content of 0.20 wt% the amount of the nanotubes contacting each other increases. This latter phenomenon drives an attenuation of the reinforcing efficiency from the highest achieved value to 209 GPa due complex and linked factors as the reduction of the transfer load efficiency between the nano-particle and the hosting matrix, a significant decrease of aspect ratio and the existence of weak point represented by the same contact point within the nanotube forming network. At high nano-filler content, clustering is revealed by the formation of very large aggregates of nanotube bundles that contributes to the further reinforcement efficiency fall. At the tubes concentration increase ($\phi > 0.1$ wt%), the clustering is producing very large aggregates of nanotubes, which contribute to the reinforcement efficiency reduction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the reinforcement effect caused by the addition of carbon nanotubes in a mono-component resin does benefit from the highest level of individual dispersion of large aspect ratio, high modulus tubes. From optical observations, on the micron scale, when the concentration pass the statistical percolation threshold, nanotubes start to

contact each other reducing the effective aspect ratio and further tend to aggregates. At higher concentrations than percolation threshold, in fact, not only particles contact is unavoidable, due to statistical considerations, but also the sticky inter-particles potential gives a rise to micron sized agglomerates acting as mechanical defects for the resulting nanocomposite.

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